

Two of the authors (M.K.) and (H.M.T.) thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of fellowships.

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Chemistry of Euphorbiaceae. Part-III†.
Isolation of Lupane Group of Triterpenes
from *Givotia rottleriformis* Griff.

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GIVOTIA *rottleriformis* Griff. (N.O. *Euphorbiaceae*) is a moderate-sized tree found in the Deccan forests. The wood is used locally for making painted toys¹. Literature survey has shown that this plant has not been examined for its crystalline principles. The bark has been examined in the present investigation.

The ether-extract of the bark furnished a brownish yellow solid (3%). It was fractionated into acidic (2.5%) and neutral (0.5%) fractions with 10% NaOH solution.

The acidic fraction was homogeneous on tlc and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 298-300°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +5^\circ$; δ 4.7 (2H, isopropylidene); m/z 446 ($C_{30}H_{48}O_8$). It was identified as betulinic acid by comparison of the compound, methyl ester (CH_3N_3 , m.p. 220-22°) and acetate (Py-Ac₂O, m.p. 290-95°) with authentic sample of betulinic acid, methyl betulinatate and acetyl betulinic acid².

The neutral fraction is not homogeneous on tlc and showed two spots. It was adsorbed on a column of silica gel (< 200 mesh) and eluted with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1, 2 dm³) and benzene (2 dm³)

successively. The petroleum ether-benzene eluate furnished lupeol (0.05%), m.p. 210-12°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +24^\circ$; δ 4.75 (2H, isopropylidene). The identity was confirmed by comparison with authentic sample³ (ir and co-tlc).

The benzene eluate furnished betulin (0.35%), m.p. 250-52°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +19^\circ$; δ 4.70 (2H, isopropylidene). The identity was confirmed by comparison with authentic sample³ (ir and co-tlc).

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Chemical Components of *Rhamnus virgata*

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EARLIER investigation¹ on *Rhamnus virgata* (Syn. *R. dahuricus*) of Rhamnaceae family has shown the presence of rhamnocitrin and rhamnazin. Since no extensive work has been carried out on *R. virgata*, we undertook its chemical examination for studying the phenolic components.

Stems (3 kg) of *R. virgata* from Solan, Himachal Pradesh (India) were extracted with hot ethanol and the extractives were chromatographed over silica gel. Elutions with petroleum ether to ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 4) afforded eight compounds. Of these, five have been characterised as chrysophanol, physcion, rhamnocitrin, kaempferol and 3-*o*-methylquercetin on the basis of spectral properties and direct comparisons. The remaining three are rare metabolites and have been labelled as A, B and C.

Compound A : It crystallised from ethyl acetate-benzene, m.p. 186-188°. Its acetate was prepared from Ac₂O-Py and crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 140-42°; δ (CDCl₃) 6.72 (1H, br s

† Part-II, 24-Nor-cyclolaudenol from *Euphorbia nivulata*, *Phytochemistry* communicated.

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H-6), 6.62 (1H, br s, H-4), 5.10 (2H, s, 2×H-3), 3.82 (3H, s, 1×OMe) and 2.32 (3H, s, phenolic acetoxy); m/z , (rel. int.) 222 (M^+ , 12), 207 (12), 194 (5), 180 (58), 179 (20), 164 (12), 163 (31), 152 (100), 137 (26), 136 (40) and 135 (70). It was characterised as 5-methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide and the identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample, supplied by Hansel who isolated^a it from *Helichrysum italicum* (compositae).

Compound B · It crystallised from ethyl acetate-benzene, m.p. 265°. Its acetate prepared from Ac_2O -Py was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether, m.p. 218-220°; δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.95 (1H, s, H-4), 7.50 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-5), 6.80 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-7), 3.90 (3H, s, OMe), 2.35 (6H, s, aromatic Me and phenolic acetoxy) and 2.30 (6H, s, two phenolic acetoxy); m/z 384 (M^+ 42), 356, 342, 328, 313, 300 and 272. It was characterised as 6-*o*-methylalaternin and the identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample, supplied by Stoessel who isolated^a it from cultures of *Alternaria porri*. It is the first report of its isolation from a plant source.

Compound C: It was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 221°; gave purple red colour with ferric chloride; did not respond to Mg/HCl test; M^+ 288, $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$; ν_{max} (KBr) 3400, 1680, 1615, 1505, 1455, 1365, 1320, 1235, 1205, 1160, 1130, 1105, 1090, 990, 925, 855, 830, 795 and 720 cm^{-1} ; its methyl ether ($Me_2SO_4/Me_2CO/K_2CO_3$), m.p. 119-20°, δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.05 (2H, d, J 8Hz, H-2', H-6'), 6.65 (2H, d, J 8Hz, H-3', H-5'), 6.05 (1H, br s, H-7), 5.85 (1H, br s, H-5), 3.85 (6H, s, 2×OMe), 3.70 (3H, s, 1×OMe), 3.25 (3H, s, 1×OMe), 3.05 (2H, s, benzylic H); tetracetate (Ac_2O/Py) δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.40 (2H, d, J

8Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.15 (2H, d, J 8Hz, H-3', H-5'), 6.88 (1H, br s, H-7), 6.72 (1H, br s, H-5), 3.34 (2H, d, benzylic), 2.50, 2.42, 2.35 and 2.25 (3H each, 4s, four acetoxy). It was identified as maesopsin, an aurone hydrate, reported⁴ earlier from *Maesopsis eminii* (Rhamnaceae).

As a further confirmation, naringenin, isolated⁶ from *Prunus puddum*, was converted⁶ into dihydrokaempferol which on treatment with 2 *N* NaOH afforded⁷ maesopsin, m.p. 221°, undepressed on admixture with compound C. Its ir was superimposable with that of compound C.

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CONTENTS, 2nd page, line 29, read,

Aquo-bis(diethyldithiocarbamato)nitrosyl Chromium(I)

Page 63, line 51, read,

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